

Title: The Need for Small Businesses to Implement Counterintelligence

Author: Julia C. Goetz | **ORCID:** <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7853-7639>

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the threats that small businesses in the United States face from foreign adversary sanctioned corporate and economic espionage, highlighting companies in innovation and defense fields who rely on intellectual property to provide profits. Small businesses are typically limited in their resources and have, if any, underdeveloped counterintelligence practices that are insufficient in countering threats. This allows foreign adversaries, especially China, Russia, and Iran, to disrupt the United States while strengthening their own respective economies. Through case examples, such as the trial of Liming Li and the FBI’s “The Company Man” production, evidence that attempts to steal intellectual property are constantly occurring is presented. This paper also identifies common misconceptions that small businesses develop, such as the belief they are too small to be targeted, that deter them from implementing counterintelligence practices. Ultimately, a defensive counterintelligence approach is recommended for small businesses to follow with a debate on offensive counterintelligence discussed.

KEYWORDS: Counterintelligence, corporate espionage, economic espionage, intellectual property, Ostrich Syndrome, James Bond Syndrome, Silo Syndrome, small business

When most Americans think of innovation, they instantly think of companies like Google, Microsoft, Tesla, and other industry leading giants. Yet, many of these industry conglomerates rely on the innovation-forward missions of small businesses in the United States. They look to acquire these small companies to boost profits and create a diverse portfolio. But giant companies are not the only ones targeting small businesses; foreign adversaries are also in the competitive market, but not to rightfully purchase the “mom and pop” businesses. Research and development in these countries is not on the same level as it is in the United States, which leads to theft and manufacturing of others' time and dedication to innovation. Why would other countries spend their own money on advancing research and development when they can just steal from naive companies in the United States? There is a solution to prevent this all too common threat: counterintelligence.

The information presented is not meant to scare small businesses, but it is meant to help them understand the reality that they are targets of corporate and economic espionage. They should not be discouraged to innovate, as their developments are the backbone of the United States economy, but they should be aware of the potential consequences and measures that can be taken against corporate and economic espionage.

Economic vs. Corporate Espionage

Understanding the differences between economic and corporate espionage allows for a precise evaluation of threats to small companies. Corporate espionage, defined as “the unlawful theft/ acquisition of intellectual property, such as key trade secret and patent information as well as industrial manufacturing techniques and processes, ideas, and formulas, is a significant target

of foreign adversaries looking to steal rather than innovate”.¹ Economic espionage is “foreign power-sponsored or coordinated intelligence activity directed at the United States government or United States corporations, establishments, or persons, designed to unlawfully or clandestinely influence sensitive economic policy decisions or to unlawfully obtain sensitive financial, trade, or economic policy information; proprietary economic information; or critical technologies”². A hybrid definition of both areas best describes the issue in this essay: foreign power-sponsored covert theft of intellectual property developed by small businesses. Though clandestine persuasion of economic policy is important, the focus of this essay will examine the potential detrimental effects of economic and corporate espionage by foreign actors on small businesses and why counterintelligence is a vital aspect to protect their intellectual property and livelihoods.

Why Small Businesses are Targeted

If companies do not properly invest in counterintelligence practices, they risk losing everything they have worked to achieve in the innovation field. Foreign adversaries focus on exploiting gaps in security and counterintelligence measures in small businesses, especially those in innovation, because they have high expenses and may not be focused on the threat to their company. This makes the small businesses susceptible to corporate espionage because they may not have the funding for ample security measures. The executives or owners of many small businesses wear blinders that focus on profits and typical business practices but they avoid,

¹“Libguides: Counterintelligence: Corporate Espionage.” Corporate Espionage - Counterintelligence - LibGuides at Naval War College, June 18, 2025.

²Libguides: Counterintelligence: Corporate Espionage.”

purposefully or naively, the threat of espionage. The fine line between success and failure preoccupies the minds of those in charge.

The United States government and economy rely heavily on the innovation from the small businesses that reside in the nation. Small companies, who in this essay will have an employee population between 1-249, stated in a study conducted by the National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics that an average of 41% of their operations included internal or external research and development³. Many of these companies, especially ones that are just starting up, do not realize the successful innovation in their respective fields becomes not only a target of consumers, but of foreign adversaries.

Foreign adversaries, prominently the Chinese Communist Party (CCP), Iran, and Russia, costs the United States between one and three percent of its \$21 trillion annual GDP through the theft of intellectual property.⁴ These adversaries look to steal more than “traditional” business secrets that may boost their economy; they look to steal patents, formulas, directions, etc. of military equipment and technology that may be used against the United States. This allows their militaries to grow stronger without the timely process of innovation. It is easy to follow directions once one has them, which is why small businesses need to implement counterintelligence in their environments.

There is another reason small companies are targeted by foreign adversaries; the latter is aware that many successful innovation companies purchase small businesses to become

³ Kindlon, Audrey E. “First Comprehensive Innovation Survey for the United States: Data from the 2017 Annual Business Survey | NSF - National Science Foundation.” National Center for Science and Engineering Statistics, July 28, 2021.

⁴ INSA’s Insider Threat Subcommittee. “Insider Threats and Commercial Espionage: Economic and National Security Impacts.” Intelligence and National Security Alliances, May 2021.

subsidiaries of their company. If the adversary can embed a nationalist within the purchased company, they may be able to get access to a much larger network of innovation. Granted, the parent company may have counterintelligence practices in place, but adversaries will likely still try to steal intellectual property and many times will try to facilitate the mergers and acquisitions⁵

Critical Foreign Adversaries Targeting United States Innovation

As briefly discussed before, the critical threats to small businesses in innovation are China, Iran, and Russia.⁶ The latter's involvement in the Russia-Ukraine War has resulted in a drop of cases, but does not mean companies should turn a blind eye⁷. Iran has continued to develop their corporate and economic espionage tradecraft especially in cyberspace. Iranian hacker group Rocket Kitten has been targeting United States private sector defense firms, specifically those that enhance missiles and space programs, through website exploitation, phishing, credential harvesting, and social engineering techniques⁸. But China, specifically the CCP, continues to be the biggest threat to small companies. A deeper dive into China will be presented later.

Small Businesses in Military Innovation

Small businesses continue to play crucial roles in the military innovation sector, allowing the United States government to rely on their ability to adapt quickly to changes in the defense industry and avoid lengthy bureaucratic processes to innovate. Of course, companies like

⁵ Palma, et. al. "US Warns Tech Start-Ups on Security Threats from Foreign Investors." Financial Times, July 24, 2024.

⁶ "Counterintelligence." FBI, May 3, 2016.

⁷ "Counterintelligence." FBI

⁸ "Foreign Economic Espionage in Cyberspace", 2018.

Lockheed Martin and Boeing are giants of the industry, but they too rely on small businesses to advance the defense industry. Boeing even has multiple programs that empower small businesses to conduct research and development on behalf of the company⁹. The programs allow the large companies to work with the small businesses to work together to innovate new products on their behalf. The large companies can't innovate every piece of military technology, which is where small businesses tend to fill in the gaps in defense. The United States has also created many programs, such as Small Business Innovation Research, and Rapid Integrated Scalable Enterprise¹⁰ that enable small businesses to pitch their defense development ideas that they may not have the funds to produce. In the defense industrial sector, 73% of the private companies are considered small businesses by the Department of Defense and 25% of prime contracts were awarded to small businesses¹¹.

One would hope the small companies conducting this critical research would have counterintelligence measures in place, but as discussed throughout this essay, this can be costly. A potential solution to his problem: government-funded counterintelligence resources for contracted companies in the defense industry. This would allow small businesses to focus expenses on innovation while being supported and trained on counterintelligence from professionals dedicated to the discipline.

One of the ways for foreign adversaries to steal intellectual property in small businesses is through insider threats. There are many examples of insider threats who provided foreign

⁹"Globalization & Supplier Development and Strategic Sourcing & Partnerships." Boeing Suppliers. Accessed July 1, 2025.

¹⁰ "Home." Office of Small Business Programs. Accessed July 15, 2025. <https://business.defense.gov/programs/>.

¹¹ Schmidt, Johannes. "How Small American Businesses Are Driving Defense Innovations." Small Business Innovation Research / Small Business Technology Transfer, April 20, 2023.

adversaries with advanced military technology that affected small businesses. In these cases, the Department of Defense ended their contract with the company, resulting in significant loss of profit¹². China is the leader in the use of insider threats to obtain military intellectual property and they have been for decades. A May 2023 case involves Liming Li who stole sensitive technology from two California-based companies that could be used in nuclear submarines and military aircraft to start his own company marketing the technology in China¹³. Li was an employee of two American manufacturing companies, the first company for twenty-two years and the second for one year, where he served in engineering, management, and software development roles throughout his career¹⁴. Although Li is not a Chinese national, he planned to voluntarily participate in the People's Republic of China's Thousand Talents Program, which recruits members of international Chinese communities in innovation careers¹⁵, and sell the intellectual property he stole to the PRC and other PRC-based organizations¹⁶. Though the CCP was not directly involved in recruiting Li, they likely would have been a customer of this technology.

Common Misperceptions of Corporate and Economic Espionage

Though many are aware of the fact that corporate and economic espionage exist, they may have common misperceptions about them that stem from faulty mindsets. These misperceptions are threats to the protection of intellectual property and can be found in companies of all sizes, but it is important to highlight them to understand how

¹² Brown, Alison. "Companies Raise Intellectual Property Protection Issues." *National Defense Magazine*, July 1, 2010.

¹³ "Justice Department Announces Five Cases as Part of Recently Launched Disruptive Technology Strike Force." Department of Justice, February 6, 2025.

¹⁴ "Justice Department Announces Five", Department of Justice.

¹⁵ "Chinese Talent Plans." FBI, November 16, 2020.

¹⁶ "Justice Department Announces Five" Department of Justice.

counterintelligence is a critical asset to counter these vulnerabilities. Small businesses, evidently, do not have as many employees as large companies and if all employees share a common misperception, there is little to no chance of breaking this static mindset, leaving room for foreign adversaries to clandestinely achieve their espionage mission. All employees, especially management, of innovative companies should be aware of these faulty mindsets and how to counter them from arising in the workplace. Falling victim to these mindsets, particularly in a small business due to low employment numbers, could lead to a static environment that does not challenge the unsecure practices of the company and may present opportunities for foreign adversaries to go undetected and target the business.

The first mindset is known as the Silo Syndrome¹⁷. This is described as the belief that corporate and economic espionage are the problem of a single department within an organization; each department is its own silo and will not be affected by others. Those who believe this misconception believe that external and even internal threats are a problem for only security and IT to worry about¹⁸. Adversaries are not looking to spy on the security or IT departments of the innovative companies, but they target the information held by the research and development groups. Counterintelligence should be practiced throughout all departments so if there is a situation, each department will know what to do and not to do and there will be a lower chance of success for the intruder.

The second mindset is James Bond Syndrome¹⁹. This syndrome sees victims believing the only form of espionage is that which is completed by James Bond-esc operators or on the

¹⁷ Wimmer, 16

¹⁸Wimmer, 16

¹⁹Ibid

opposite end, by computer science nerds hiding out in basements²⁰. Many successful business espionage operations use relatively simple tradecraft, such as eavesdropping or looking through unoccupied emails, that take advantage of a businesses lack of not only counterintelligence, but basic security measures. This misconception also affects the media coverage given to economic and corporate espionage since most of the tradecraft involved is not as exciting as that used in James Bond films. This lack of media coverage creates an uninformed environment, a contributor to the next mindset.

The last mindset to be discussed is the Ostrich Syndrome²¹. This is the belief by any member of a business that, based solely on “hope” and not fact, their organization will not be a target to economic or corporate espionage, just as an ostrich believes sticking its’ head in the sand will eliminate the threat²². This false hope is amplified for small businesses since many employees or owners believe they are too small and diluted within a large community of innovative groups; this is far from the truth. Since there are more small businesses than large, there are more typically low security targets for foreign adversaries.

Many executives of companies believe that they do not have anything worth stealing within their company, but that is not true because if they did not, they would not be competitive in their field and hence would not exist²³. Adversaries are always looking to take the cheap and easy way and will jump through many hoops to steal what may seem like miniscule innovations.

²⁰Ibid

²¹ Wimmer, 17

²² Wimmer, 17

²³ Ibid

A Focus on China

China is constantly looking to “innovate” new products across all markets, innovate meaning stealing intellectual property, patents, formulas, and other intangible assets from United States small and large companies. China wants to increase their domestic production in critical areas such as technology, defense, agriculture, etc. and provide a competitive edge in international markets. They do not want to continue to improve the economies of their foreign adversaries by purchasing their products, blueprints, etc., so they rely on corporate espionage to make their “own” products²⁴. The CCP is taking advantage of the free society the United States allows its citizens to be innovative in and then using it against them, both economically and militarily²⁵.

In 2015, The PRC announced a ten-year plan to improve the innovation and manufacturing ecosystem within the nation, creating a *Made in China 2025* initiative.²⁶ The plan is inspired by Germany’s *Industry 4.0* initiative, which focuses on incorporating “smart” technology into the innovation and manufacturing sectors, and looks to improve Chinese innovation and manufacturing on all levels, including municipal and small businesses²⁷. But the program has not met the expectations formed in 2015. Systematic design flaws have led to “duplication of investment across regions, misaligned local incentives, overreliance on subsidies, and an excessive focus on the production side of the economy at the expense of household

²⁴ Kuo, “Made in China 2025”.

²⁵ “The China Threat.” FBI, July 10, 2020.

²⁶ Kuo, Kaiser. “Made in China 2025 Set the Tempo of China’s Industrial Ambitions.” World Economic Forum, June 26, 2025.

²⁷ Kuo, “Made in China 2025”.

demand”.²⁸ This had led to China’s continued reliance on foreign technology and innovation in critical areas, such as semi-conductors and advanced aircraft.²⁹

In 2019, the FBI published a brief document bringing awareness to the threat of China within United States innovation companies. The document discusses the aforementioned *Made in China 2025* plan and its disruption to the American economy.

China sought to significantly reduce reliance on foreign-produced technology and begin to develop within their own nation. The industries can be described as cutting edge and include: information technology, computer numerical

control machine tools and robotics, aerospace

equipment, marine engineering equipment and high-

tech ships, advance rail transportation equipment, energy-efficient and new-energy automobiles,

electric power equipment, agricultural equipment, new materials, and biomedicine and high-

performance medical instruments³⁰. It is now 2025 and China is still conducting economic and

corporate espionage operations in the United States so they may “grow” in the previously

mentioned industries. Natural growth in industry is a good thing, but China’s espionage

operations create disruption to global markets and make the United States less competitive,

especially since China does not have labor laws and manufactures products at a higher rate.

Source: “China: The Risk to Corporate America.” FBI

²⁸ Ibid

²⁹ Ibid

³⁰ “China: The Risk to Corporate America.” FBI, October 4, 2019.

In the same document, the FBI highlights the areas of business that China, or any foreign adversary, may target including financial, employee, and customer data, business strategies, blueprints, prototypes, equipment specifications, and more³¹. These are only a few of the areas

Source: "China: The Risk to Corporate America." FBI

the Chinese attempt to infiltrate, but can be combated via counterintelligence practices.

Case Study: FBI's *The Company Man*

The FBI has released many videos and articles loosely detailing cases of counterintelligence against foreign adversaries to bring awareness to the reality of economic and corporate espionage. The case that will be studied here is titled *The Company Man* and is based on an actual case built by the FBI³². It is a classic case of the use of MICE (money, ideology, coercion, and ego, the four most common sources used to recruit spies) by the CCP and is an example of their persistence when they do not get what they aim for.

DIFFERENCES IN BUSINESS PRACTICES	
UNITED STATES	CHINA
GENERALLY ACCESSIBLE MARKET	HIGHLY RESTRICTIVE MARKET
MARKET ECONOMY	STATE-RUN ECONOMY
DEVELOPMENT BY INNOVATION	DEVELOPMENT BY THEFT, REPLICATION, AND COMMERCIALIZATION
INDEPENDENT JUDICIARY AND SEPARATION OF POWERS	JUDICIARY SUBORDINATE TO THE GOVERNMENT
LAWS PROTECTING INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY	THEFT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY
NO GOVERNMENT-SPONSORED ECONOMIC ESPIONAGE	GOVERNMENT-SPONSORED ECONOMIC ESPIONAGE

What appears to be two Chinese business people visit and have a meeting at a United States small business who have innovated a new manufacturing process in the glass insulation

³¹ "China: Risk to Corporate", FBI.

³² "The Company Man: Protecting America's Secrets | Federal Bureau of Investigation." FBI, July 23, 2015.

industry. The United States company is looking to finalize the production process in China and meet with the Chinese businessmen. During the meeting, one of the businessmen leaves to use the restroom and is caught looking through an employee's computer. The meeting is immediately terminated and no further negotiations are pursued. This is the first Chinese failure and successful counterintelligence measure of the American company.

The failure did not stop the Chinese businessmen from attempting to steal the intellectual property. That same night, they are caught lurking around the manufacturing facility, taking pictures of equipment inside of a garage. The men are immediately chased from the area and the glass company employees notify their superiors. This raises more red flags for the company, who rely on their innovation for competitive edge in the market. Another success for them.

Still not successful in their attempts to steal intellectual property, the businessmen move to their next target: a disgruntled employee. The employee is not going to get a promised promotion and is financially struggling, the perfect target for the CCP. The businessmen reach out to the employee to offer him a position at a glass manufacturing company in China where he will make a significant amount of money in exchange for his services. Uncomfortable and educated on the threat of economic espionage, the employee turns down the offer and reports the interaction to his superiors, hence the nickname The Company man for his loyalty to his company.

This engagement saw the executives of the glass company report all three interactions to the FBI, who were then able to identify and arrest the businessmen for espionage. This case is a great example of how counterintelligence practices and training can save a company from devastation at the hands of the CCP.

Counterintelligence Practices: Defensive

An important distinction to make before diving into counterintelligence practices is the difference between security measures and counterintelligence. Security measures that contribute to strong counterintelligence but are not necessarily the latter include simple tasks: locking doors, enforcing a clear-desk policy, signing out of computers when away from a desk, preventing piggybacking into an office are all examples of this. These are everyday regulations that any respectable business will have in place to keep their company safe.

When the idea of defensive counterintelligence is brought up, many think it is a reactionary method to an event that has occurred. This is true, but there are many ways for defensive counterintelligence to be proactive. This requires much planning that includes all employees of a small business, no matter their role in the company, to participate. As discussed in The Company Man case study, the proactiveness of the glass company prevented an act of corporate espionage within the company; the executives immediately terminated the meeting when the Chinese businessman was caught “checking his email”, the overnight factory workers took action when they spotted the Chinese businessmen taking photos of products, and the targeted employee knew that the employment opportunity offered to him was abnormal. The company planned for potential intrusions, consulted with the FBI regarding the Chinese businessmen, and trained their employees on the signs of espionage.

Planning is the foundation of counterintelligence practices in any business, government agency, or potential target of espionage. It identifies the most valuable and vulnerable targets, whether it is people, physical locations, databases, etc. that foreign nations may look to expose within the business and the countermeasures that can be taken. Of course, it is impossible to have

a detailed plan for every attempt at economic espionage, but planning can help relieve chaos that may ensue. Hank Prunckun gives a format for defensive counterintelligence planning in his work *Counterintelligence: Theory and Practice* that can be used by small businesses. The plan includes six steps:

1. Identify and locate sensitive information that requires protection
2. Identify the threat-agent(s)
3. Explore vulnerabilities to the threat(s)
4. Gauge the likelihood that the threat(s) will eventuate
5. Assess the consequence the threat(s) will have
6. Construct a prevention, preparation, response, and recovery plan³³

If small businesses take time to go through this list, they can significantly reduce the chance of

falling victim to corporate espionage by foreign adversaries, and even domestic competitors. To focus on the identifying of threats, it is important to understand what constitutes a threat. Prunckun provides a logical model for threat that allows users

to visualize the characteristics of a threat. After discovering the threats within the small business, the company must then complete steps three through six to properly counter the threat.

Step six can seem daunting, especially to small businesses who typically do not have many resources in counterintelligence. But there are many resources provided by the FBI that can be used to help form this PPRR plan. The FBI is aware of the threat that foreign adversaries

³³ Prunckun, 66

pose to small businesses and continue to provide support to the protection of intellectual property. Another idea for small businesses to develop a PPRR plan is to consult counterintelligence practices and lessons learned from counterintelligence failures with each other. Though the small companies may be competing with each other in the market, they all, hopefully, share the common goal of protecting their intellectual property from foreign adversaries.

An Ethical Debate: US Offensive Counterintelligence

As the CCP continues to unapologetically take advantage of United States innovation in the private sector, a question should be raised if the United States should be involved in offensive counterintelligence in the same area. Many would argue intellectual espionage does not prevent physical harm as “traditional” espionage does, so there is no need for the United States to participate in offensive counterintelligence. But what happens to American and allied military forces fighting against the technology that was developed and stolen from small companies? Countering a weapon with the same weapon will result in a waste of resources, but what happens to the United States when they run out of these resources and the CCP, a large manufacturing hub, has produced a higher amount of product and has a military advantage against the United States? Casualties will likely occur and the United States will be at a disadvantage because of intellectual theft. If offensive counterintelligence in intellectual espionage can prevent this chaos, should the United States engage in it?

At this point, one may ask what would be involved in offensive counterintelligence against the CCP. There are many applications of offensive counterintelligence that could be successful to the mission. One application that would be beneficial to small businesses with the help of the United States government is to lure in Chinese nationals to “work” for their company.

Advertisements can be created showing the “advanced technology” and “innovative research” the company works on, becoming a landing spot for the CCP. If the CCP sends a nationalist to the company, the United States could track every move the nationalist makes and follow the audit trail back to the Chinese source. The information collected by the nationalist would be false and contain malware to conduct surveillance on Chinese intelligence. This would allow the United States to have a better idea of where intellectual property is precisely sent to and may prevent theft.

Many will argue that offensive counterintelligence is unnecessary and even a violation of the morals that the United States holds itself to. An argument may be made that the protection of intellectual property is not worth the investment as it does not affect the national security of the citizens of the United States. Intellectual property is just a “thing” or “intangible” that does not compare to the protection of human life. As discussed throughout this essay, this is not true: intellectual property is more than a “thing” and if not actively protected, offensively and defensively, foreign adversaries will be at a greater advantage in military technology and other critical infrastructure developments. This is what will harm the American people.

Conclusion

Loss on profits can be affected by more than inflation, tariffs, and other business-centric terms heard in the news today, a lesson that small businesses need to learn when developing critical intellectual property. Corporate espionage presents an instant risk of loss that cannot be recovered by small businesses, as the intellectual property that they develop is the core of their earnings. As small businesses lose, so does the United States economy and the spirit of innovation begins to fade away. If foreign adversaries continue to steal intellectual property,

small businesses lose their purpose to innovate and the former have not only financially and militarily advanced, but they have psychologically succeeded. Counterintelligence and its suggested applications can significantly reduce the risk of intellectual theft, but regularly maintaining and advancing practices must continue. The United States continues to be a target for theft of intellectual property, especially small businesses who have limited counterintelligence resources. But have the government, media, and even larger companies who oftentimes rely on the innovation that small businesses develop?